

THE ROLE OF QUALITY-MAKING WEIGHTS IN THE WORK "MEHROBDAN CHAYON"

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7897091>

Abstract: In the lexicon of the Uzbek language, all-Arabic words form the majority. Especially in the lexicon, the amount of words belonging to the noun phrase category is high. They have their own semantic features. Arabic words represent more scientific, religious, moral, educational, abstract concepts.

Key words: Uzbek language, word, assimilation, lexicon, language, educational, semantic, concepts.

РОЛЬ КАЧЕСТВЕННОГО ИЗГОТОВЛЕНИЯ ВЕСОВ В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИИ "СКОРПИОН С АЛТАРЯ"

Аннотация: В лексике узбекского языка общеарабские слова составляют большинство. Особенно в лексиконе велико количество слов, принадлежащих к категории именных словосочетаний. Они имеют свои смысловые особенности. Арабские слова представляют более научные, религиозные, моральные, образовательные, абстрактные понятия.

Ключевые слова: узбекский язык, слово, ассимиляция, лексика, язык, образование, семантика, понятия.

INTRODUCTION

The importance of external sources is important in the enrichment of the vocabulary content of the Uzbek language. The phenomenon of word acquisition occurs on the basis of various economic, socio-political, spiritual and educational relations between peoples. The Arabic word layer of the lexicon of the Uzbek language is borrowed in a historical-traditional way.

The assimilation of Arabic words began in the 8th century and was much more active from the 9th to the 10th centuries. The factors that led to the adoption of the word from Arabic are: first of all, the Arab conquest, the prevalence of Islam, the beginning of the use of Arabic writing, the teaching of Arabic in madrasas, the creation of the scholar-he fuzalos in Arabic, the composition of the Turkic-Arabic bilingualism.

In the lexicon of the Uzbek language, all-Arabic words form the majority. Especially in the lexicon, the amount of words belonging to the noun phrase category is high. They have their own semantic features. Arabic words represent more scientific, religious, moral, educational, abstract concepts. One group of Arabic cognitions in our language has changed the value of meaning and become another word unrelated to etymological meaning and understanding, or there has been an expansion of meaning and a narrowing of meaning. In Abdullah Qadiri's "Scorpio from Love", arabisms in qualitative weights were widely used.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In Arabic, words formed from a verb that show characteristics inherent in both the verb and the adjective - "nouns made of the verb" - are considered adjectives: Secretary, teacher, mansur, abstract, said, like proportional. In Uzbek, adjectives change depending on the tense, while in Arabic the opposite - past and present-have the same form for the next tense.

The adjectival form of the Arabic verb is equivalent to the adjectival form of the verb in Uzbek, but in many places comes the adjective. For example: *Mohmal – vague, proud, gentle, short, hypocritical, special, like a deceased. But in Arabic, adjectives form nouns-nouns made of the verb, in addition to masdars, adjectives, place and time names, work-weapons, professional names.*

There are clear and majhul forms of adjectives, which are formed in different weights.

The exact ratio adjectival of the verb chapter I **fā'il(un)** it is formed in weight and denotes the performer of the action - the subject, into Uzbek «...gan», «...kan», «...qan», «...yotgan» with adjectival suffixes, or ...*chi* translated with the suffix otted: *Secretary - "doer of writing", forig' – "unoccupied", zomin – "guarantor", Noel – "possessor (grower), zoe' - as lost, wasted. There was also the possibility that the God would be the heir to the throne if the son would grant a nephew ("Mehrobdan chayon).*

Majhul is formed in the weight of the relative adjective **maf'ul(un)**, and the object of action, the object, expresses the result that occurs through action: oppressed - oppressed, oppressed, responsible – requested, meaning – meaning, like majruh – injured. "Well done," said Anwar — "I will be almost happy with this day's guest," I look like a stranger (*M/ch*).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Grammatical features specific to the definite and plural relation apply to adjectives in all chapters, with the definite relation indicating the subject, the object or result of the plural relation being the object of action: *kātib(un)* – writer, who writes; *maktūb(un)* – as written.

The verb Chapter II is formed in the weight of the definite relative adjective Mafa'il(un), the adjective majhul relative Mafa'al(un): author, muallaq, institution, muattar, muyassar, founder. The exact ratio form indicates the executor of the action: mudarris - like a lecturer, muazzin – like a deacon, astrologer – like a diviner depending on the stars. The Majhul ratio form represents the fulfillment of the work-action, the result that has occurred, the sign: hanging – put in a pedestal, as if given a muzayyan – blind. - Such" founder " exhortations did not blind Anvar either (*M/ch*).

Chapter II verb most of the adjectives of the exact ratio represent the noun word category in our language: teacher, muwaqqid, mudarris, mukarrir (assistant, Assistant), muse, editor, teacher, author, like muganny. Majhul ratio adjectives have passed into the adjectival word category: muazzam, certain, muattar, muzaffar, mukarram.

From the verb Chapter III, the definite ratio adjective mafā'il(un), the majhul relative adjective mafā'al (un) is formed in weight: baraka – bāraka - mubārak. According to, such words as Mudam, muzofot, mulozim, hypocritical are adjectival forms of the verb Chapter III, which is borrowed into Uzbek. ...the gentle gaze of a young scientist was still attached to the mutoyabah of two Mufti, whose meaning of Gaul lay on his face (*M/ch*).

Chapter IV adjective **muf'il(un), muf'al(un)** formed in their weight: *xabara – baxbara – muxbir(un)*. Now that he himself has entered the age of forty, he has been living with this wax Earth for twenty-five years (*M/ch*).

The adjectival form of the verb Chapter V **mutafa'il(un), mutafa'al(un)** produced by their weight: *fakara – tafakkara – mutafakkir(un)*. Words such as specialist, thinker, thinker, mutavalli are adjectives formed from the verb chapter V. One of the mutawaffo mirzos of the Khan horde had a son who was reading in the madrasa ...(*M/ch*).

In the work, arabisms were also widely used in the adjectival weights of the verbs VI, VII and VIII.

CONCLUSION

Both adjectives of the verb Chapter IX *muf'all(un)* it is formed in weight. The verb Chapter IX is formed from adjectives denoting a color or physical property and means to embody that color or property. For example, *asvad(un)* - black; *musvadd(un)* - as if darkened. In "Mehrobdan chayon", arabisms in the adjective weight of the verb Title IX were not observed. In our language, words borrowed from the verb Chapter IX of the Arabic language hardly occur.

Definite and plural relative adjectives of the verb Chapter X *mustaf'il(un)*, *mustafa'al(un)* is formed in weight: *malaka – mustamlakun – mustamlaka*. Adjectives such as strong, independent, except, independent, colonial are formed from the verb chapter X.

From the above, it can be said that many adjectival forms of words have been borrowed from Arabic into Uzbek. Such words are embedded in the vocabulary of the Uzbek language in such a way that it is often not even noticeable that they are arabic assimilations.

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